

A Synthesis of Oxypalmatine: Dehydro- nor-oxy- ψ -coralydin.

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The method which was successful in the synthesis of the oxyberberine (*cf.* Perkin, Ray and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 740) is now applied for the preparation of oxy-palmatine. Palmatine differs from berberine in that the methylene-dioxy group of the latter is replaced by two methoxyl groups in the former alkaloid. It is clear that it should be possible to convert berberine into palmatine. Feist and Sandstede (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1918, 256, 1) failed to effect this but Späth and Lang (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 3064) succeeded to a limited extent in converting tetrahydroberberine into tetrahydropalmatine by heating the former with potassium hydroxide in methyl alcohol and methylating the resulting product with methyl sulphate and alkali in absence of oxygen. The doubt thrown on the synthesis of berberine by Haworth, Perkin and Rankin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1686) necessitated a fresh synthesis of the alkaloid. It was thought that the application of the same method would lead to a synthesis of oxypalmatine. In the present paper this is described. Recently, while this work was in progress, Späth and Quietensky (*Ber.*, 1925, 58 B, 2267) reinvestigated their original synthesis of palmatine.*

The starting point in the present investigation has been meconone carboxylic acid (Perkin, Ray and Robinson, *loc. cit.*) on the one hand and 3 : 4-dimethoxyphenylethylamine on the other. The amide (1) prepared by condensation of the chloride of the acid with the amine

is converted into a dihydro-*iso*quinoline derivative by the prolonged

* The present paper was read before the Indian Science Congress on the 7th January, 1927. Haworth, Koepfli and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 131, 548) since then obtained oxypalmatine by a totally different method. However, the substance isolated by these authors seems to be not quite pure as it melts about 11° lower than the compound described in this paper.

action of phosphoryl chloride. A small amount of a neutral product is produced as an insoluble ochreous precipitate on decomposing the reaction mixture with ice as in the case of the synthesis of oxyberberine, together with the basic dihydro-*iso*quinoline derivative (II) as a bright yellow solution of its hydrochloride.

This neutral product similar to that obtained in the oxyberberine synthesis has now been purified and crystallised. This is chloronoroxy-berberine (III) as was suggested in the former paper.

The isolation of this compound suggests that a more direct synthesis of palmatine is desirable than that accomplished by Späth and Quietensky as here one of the methoxyl groups is eliminated instead of the methylene-dioxy group which Späth and Quietensky assumed to have been spitted off in that case. The dihydro-*iso*quinoline compound is reduced with zinc and acetic acid when oxypalmatine (IV) is produced. This compound melts at 194°-196° and gives bluish-violet fluorescence in neutral organic solvents.

An examination of the formula (IV) reveals the fact that it is very similar to a compound described by Pictet and Chou (*Ber.*, 1916, 49, 370) which they have named dehydronoroxyberberine (V) m.p.

190°. The two substances only differ in the position of the methoxyl groups.

The compound (V) was synthesised by Pictet and Chou from papaverine. They condensed papaverine with methylal as in their berberine synthesis (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2086) and the product on treatment with alkali subsequent to oxidation by iodine is (V). It has been shown by Haworth, Perkin and Bankin (*loc. cit.*) that these condensations (*cf.* the synthesis of berberine) take place with the aid of the hydrogen atom in position 2 of the veratryl nucleus whilst Pictet and Gams claimed that the hydrogen atom in position 6 reacted. It is significant that in interpreting the very similar condensation with papaverine, Pictet and Chou use the hydrogen atom in position 2 for ring closure and not the one at 6 as in their berberine synthesis.

The purification of the base (II) has proved to be difficult as in the previous case. This seems to be due to ready oxidisability (by air in presence of alkali) observed in similar cases where a carbon atom is attached to position 1 of the *isoquinoline* nucleus (*cf.* Buck, Haworth and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2176). The annexed scheme will indicate the process.

The isolation of dioxerberberine in one experiment (*cf.* Perkin, Ráy and Robinson, *loc. cit.*) can be easily understood from an examination of the above scheme taken from the paper of Buck, Haworth and Perkin. The dihydro-*isoquinoline* base is being prepared with the idea of oxidising it to stage (VII) and then effecting the ring closure to dioxypalmatine and dioxerberberine. This has been partially successful in the latter case.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3:4-Dimethoxyphenylethylamine.—This amine has been prepared by Mannich and Jacobson (*Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 189) Rosenmund Mannich and Jacobson [D. R. P. 247906, (1912)], whose methods were found to be not entirely satisfactory. The amine is best prepared by Hoffmann's reaction from 3:4-dimethoxyphenyl propionamide under the conditions described by Buck and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 1679). The preparation of this amide has been described by Buck and Perkin (*loc. cit.*) who record the unsuitability of preparing it from the acid chloride. However, under the conditions specified below it can be used with success.

The 3:4-dimethoxycinnamic acid was prepared by heating veratric aldehyde (50 g.), malonic acid (65 g.), pyridine (100 c.c.) and piperidine (5 c.c.) on the steam-bath for an hour and then the reaction completed by boiling the solution for 5 minutes. The product was cooled, poured into water and acidified with hydrochloric acid and the nearly quantitative yield of dimethoxycinnamic acid collected. This was reduced by 2½% sodium amalgam as prescribed by Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1080). The well-dried 3:4-dimethoxyhydrocinnamic acid (50 g.) was mixed with benzene (200 c.c.) and small portions of thionyl chloride (40 c.c.) added from time to time with shaking. The mixture is allowed to remain for 24 hours, moisture being excluded. The excess of thionyl chloride and benzene was then removed under greatly reduced pressure at 35° as far as possible. The residue is then dissolved in a little fresh benzene and poured cautiously to a well cooled solution containing sodium hydroxide (15 g.) and concentrated ammonia (600 c.c.). The benzene is removed by distillation and the amide crystallised from hot water, m.p. 121°—122°. The yield averages 28-30 g. The yield is better with smaller quantities. Meconine carboxylic acid and its chloride were prepared exactly as described by Perkin, Rây and Robinson (*loc. cit.*).

Preparation of the Amide (I).—The chloride prepared from meconine carboxylic acid (10 g.), in benzene (35 c.c.) was mixed with a solution of homoveratryl amine (10 g.) in benzene (40 c.c.) and pyridine (4 c.c.). The mixture was cooled and not allowed to become warm. After staying for 24 hours, the reaction was completed by warming on the steam-bath for 10 minutes. The product well

washed successively with water, sodium carbonate solution, and dilute hydrochloric acid is freed from benzene and crystallised twice from hot dilute alcohol, m.p. 185°. (Found: N, 3.07. $C_{11}H_{11}O_7N$ requires N, 3.5 per cent.).

Oxypalmatine.—Meconine carboxy- β -veratrylethylamide (I) (4 g.) and freshly distilled phosphoryl chloride (30 c.c.) were gently heated together on the steam-bath for 8 hours. The mixture after remaining for 12 hours was decomposed by crushed ice and water and the liquid filtered from small residue. The bright yellow filtrate was rendered faintly alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution under strong cooling. The ochreous faintly yellowish base was collected. This was not crystallised and was directly reduced with acetic acid (50 c.c.) and zinc dust (20 g. added in two equal portions) by boiling for 30 minutes. The filtered solution was concentrated on the water-bath and then diluted with water. This was repeatedly extracted with relatively large volume of ether. The dried ethereal solution was concentrated and the residue dissolved in a little of alcohol and treated with potassium hydroxide (1 g.) in water (5 c.c.) for 5 minutes at about 70°. Water (150 c.c.) was now introduced and the precipitate collected. This was thrice crystallised from boiling alcohol with the aid of charcoal. The substance crystallises in pale yellow woolly needles, m. p. 194°–196°.* (Found: C, 68.4; H, 5.9. $C_{21}H_{21}O_8N$ requires C, 68.6; H, 5.7 per cent.).

The substance exhibits a strong bluish-violet fluorescence in strong daylight. The solution of the substance in 50% sulphuric acid gives with a drop of nitric acid on dilution a bright purple colour. This is much deeper than the corresponding colour obtained with oxyberberine and is more stable. The substance gives a much stabler acetate than oxyberberine.

The insoluble residue obtained in the above experiment was crystallised from acetic acid and was found to contain chlorine. The substance was not obtained in sufficient quantity for detailed investigation. Therefore the similar compound obtained in the case of oxyberberine was prepared in larger quantity and investigated (cf. Perkin, Rây and Robinson, *loc. cit.*, p. 744). The substance

* Haworth, Koepfi and Perkin describes it as buff coloured prisms, m. p. 183°. The substance found in the present investigation was compared with oxyberberine and except that the two substances had different m. p.s no other difference in properties physical and chemical could be detected.

(III) crystallised in yellow rectangular prisms from acetic acid (thrice), then from benzene and finally from ethyl acetate, m. p. 229°–230°. (Found: C, 61·85; H, 4·1; N, 3·98. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires C, 61·45; H, 3·8; N, 3·8 per cent.)*

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